

IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

J.F. Liceaga
Scientific Manager
INASMET
Barrio de Igara, s/n
20.009 SAN SEBASTIAN
SPAIN

and

J.J. Imaz San Miguel
Materials Department
INASMET
Barrio de Igara, s/n
20.009 SAN SEBASTIAN
SPAIN

A B S T R A C T

This paper deals with the problem of impact behaviour of composite laminates. The suitability of composites as candidate materials for multiple applications is strongly affected by their impact properties. We have studied the influence of different processing variables on these properties.

The measurement of impact strength is obtained by the Charpy impact test, also measuring the Ductility Index defined by Beaumont et al., and the influence of processing on this Index. The influence of impact direction is also studied, as well as the different mechanisms of fracture of observed. Glass fibre reinforced epoxy is the material used for laminate fabrication.

The results show the processing relationship and impact properties, and the important influence of the impact direction on the energy values and fracture mechanism.

I N T R O D U C T I O N

At present, composite materials are utilized in multiple fields, where they have been accepted as engineering materials. The ability to resist impact by foreign object is an important design characteristic of Composite Laminates. Although the response of composite materials and structures to static load are well established, no comparable studies are available for response of Composite Laminates against foreign - impact object. One of the most important difficulties for applying these materials to impact conditions, is the

great deal of variables which influence on absorbed energy. Temperature will have a prominent influence on composite materials strength by foreign objects. It is also expected that laminate processing variables will influence impact energy of the material, that is to say, the variables used in the compression process. Finally, the impact study for composite laminates is complicated by the characteristic anisotropy of this materials. A different direction of pendulum strike, originates possibly a different damage mechanism and, consequently, different values in the necessary energy to break the laminate.

The aim of this work is to contribute in several aspects to study of the variables which influence the impact energy of a composite laminate, as well as the analysis of the different damage mechanisms that appear in the impact fracture.

The variables which have been studied are processing variables and the impact direction. The influence of temperature on impact energy and damage mechanism is being studied at this moment in our laboratory, and the results are not enclosed.

After impact energy, the ductility index has been studied too. The objective of the use of this index is to characterize the damage mechanism, analysing the brittleness or toughness in the fracture of the composite laminate.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An E-glass type cloth, 50% of fibres in the warp direction and 50% in the fill direction, was used as reinforcement for the matrix, which was an epoxy resin. The glass content of the composite laminates was 60 wt%.

50 preimpregnated reinforcement layers were stacked in order to prepare the laminate by hot press moulding, so that all laminates had a nominal thickness of 10.00 mm. The pressing of stacked sheets was done in a press of 10 T, with a flat mould. This flat mould was heated by electric resistance, in order to obtain adequate temperatures in the mould.

The applied total pressure was varied between 2.1 and 2.4 MPa. This pressure was not instantaneously applied. An adequate rate was programmed in order to reach the maximum pressure 20 minutes after the initiation of the process. The pressure thus obtained, was maintained at this constant value during the pressing.

The process time, in it's total value, was varied between 90 and 130 minutes.

Temperature, which was maintained constant during the pressing, was raised 15 minutes before the end of the process, in order to obtain a high degree of polymerisation.

For this reason, the laminate obtained by this process, was post-cured, introducing it into an oven, at 175°C for 10 hours. Thus a completely reticulated laminate is obtained, ready to study and characterize.

The temperature interval studied for measuring the

influence of this process variable on impact properties of the material was varied between 130 and 170° C. Impact tests were carried out on standardized unnotched specimens, according to ASTM Standard, with dimensions of 10X10X55 mm, using an Charpy Impact Test Machine, Tinius Olsen. The test machine is instrumented, which records the applied force and the impact energy against test time. The striker velocity was 5,12 m/sec at impact.

After impact testing, all fractures samples were carefully examined in order to select the type of damage mechanism. Several samples were examined by Scanning Electron Microscopy. For better observation, the fractured samples were previously metallised.

The curves of the absorbed impact energy and the load applied by the striker, against the time, were recorded. The curve load versus time shows a peak, the highest applied load. Beaumont et al(1), consider two different fracture periods in this curve. The area below the curve before the first peak, or the absorbed energy before the downfall of the load, means the necessary energy for initiating the fracture. Therefore, this energy is elastic, because smaller energies do not originate fracture initiation and the material restores this energy. However, the area below the curve load vs. time, after the first peak, means the energy necessary for propagating the fracture. It is a plastic energy, because the material doesn't recover the damage produced. The more ductile the material, the energy consumed to extend the crack is greater with relation to the energy consumed in the fracture initiation, so that an infinitely ductile material should have an infinite ratio between propagation energy and initiation energy.

If this reasoning is accepted, a completely brittle material doesn't have propagation energy. Therefore, all the absorbed energy is consumed in the fracture initiation. The Ductility Index is defined by the ratio between the area after the peak and the area below the curve before the peak. The brittler the material, it's Ductility Index is lower and this index is greater for ductile materials. We have measured this area for each specimen, obtaining the Ductility Index for all the materials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the different processing conditions and test methods are shown.

3.1 Influence of processing variables.

The first results studied show the variation in the total energy necessary to break the specimen in the Charpy pendulum. This variation has been produced by the change in processing variables (2) these values have been obtained when the striker impacts in a perpendicular direction to the laminate stacking plane.

Firstly if we analyse the curve which represents impact energy vs. processing temperature, we can see a maximum in the curve. This maximum indicates the best processing temperature when the temperature values are smaller, impact energy is smaller too. That could be explained by taking into account that the resin is insufficiently polymerised and therefore the necessary energy to delaminate the specimen is lower. When the processing temperature is higher than the maximum of the curve, a light degradation of the resin is to be expected. This degradation is observed in the smaller energy values necessary to break the material.

The impact energy vs. cure time curve shows a similar form with respect to the previous curve. In order to explain this curve, we can say that the low values of the impact energy at low time are originated by an inadequately curing of the resin.

In the impact energy vs. processing pressure curve (FIG 1) we can observe an increase in the impact strength material as the pressure is increased. Subsequently, a higher pressure increase originates a light decrease in the impact energy. An increase in the impact energy is expected when adherence between layers stronger. The subsequent decrease could be explained by a loss of a percentage of the resin because of an excess of pressure. This resin loss can give rise to a decrease of the adherence between layers, and consequently a decrease of the impact energy values.

With respect to variation of the ductility index when processing variables are changed, it is remarkable that the maximum of the ductility index corresponds to the maximum in the energy impact curve (FIG 2). In order to explain this coincidence, it is noted that most of the energy corresponding to the area below the F-t curve after the peak is produced by delamination of the pressed layers. Inadequate processing variables (pressure, temperature or cure time), originate the decrease in the adhesion between layers, that is to say, a smaller delamination energy. Therefore, the ratio between fracture propagation energy and initiation energy is decreasing, and the ductility index is lower. The material has become brittle due to an inadequate processing.

3.2 Influence of impact direction.

Damage mechanism depends strongly on the plane where the pendulum strikes. At the first position, we have placed the specimen so that the striker impacts in perpendicular direction to the laminate stacking plane. When the striker has impacted in this direction and the specimen is broken, the observation of fracture surface indicates delamination has been the preferential mechanism of the fracture. Consequently the values of impact energy are high, because delamination is the fracture mechanism. This delamination is shown in the enclosed figure - 3.

However, when the striker impacts in parallel direction to laminate stacking plane, the absorbing energy has significantly low values. This is due to the fact that in this fracture type, delamination doesn't appear, and the specimen breaks by tension on the fibres. This tension fracture

originates energy values appreciably lower than the values produced when the striker had knocked in a perpendicular direction to the laminate stacking plane. Figure - 4

This fracture on the specimen has been examined by Scanning Electron Microscopy, and the tension fracture type can be observed in the enclosed figure - 5.

In order to analyse the behaviour of the impact curves in these two different fracture types, we can see that force vs. time curve may be utilized for material failure identification. The force vs. time curve corresponding to the specimen where the striker impacted in a perpendicular direction to the laminate stacking plane showed successive peaks after the maximum peak, which extended during the whole time period.

This peaks describe the force downfall caused by successive delaminations. However with the specimen in which the striker knocks in a parallel direction to the laminate stacking plane, the curve force vs. time shows a maximum peak which falls suddenly, almost without other successive peaks. This curve indicates delamination is absent in the fracture mechanism.

The Ductility Index varied for these different fracture mechanisms too. Thus, a high Ductility Index characterizes the fracture by delamination, because delamination of successive layers originates a high propagation energy. On the other hand, the specimen where the striker knocks in a parallel direction to the laminate stacking plane shows a strong brittleness, or a low value of the Ductility Index Table - 1.

Finally, it is remarkable that the fracture mechanism (by delamination or fracture of the fibre by tension) depends only on the direction where the striker impacts independently of the processing variables which have been studied (pressure, temperature, and cured time).

3.3 Influence of temperature impact test.

In order to study all the parameters that influence impact resistance, we think it would be interesting to analyse the influence of temperature on these aspects (3). At the moment, we are investigating this influence, and we don't present any results. We are doing the Charpy Impact Test for several temperatures, from -195° C to 200° . We are studying different damage mechanisms, changing temperature, in order to measure temperature influence on this fracture and on absorbed energy values too.

It is interesting as well, to study the variation of Ductility Index along this temperature range. This study permits the detection of any ductile brittle transitions, which is very important for structural design.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the following points may be emphasized

4.1 There are several damage mechanisms in a fabric laminate composite, but delamination is the most usual.

Delamination is identified by a very high ductility index, which indicates high absorbed energy at impact. This energy is employed to separate the layers. When there is no delamination, absorbed energy is low, and behaviour of the laminate is like a brittle material.

4.2 Processing variables of the laminate influence delamination strength, and therefore impact energy too. To reach the most adequate energy properties in the composite laminate, we must adapt processing variables. The variables we have to vary are basically three: moulding pressure, moulding temperature and cure time.

If the variables are incorrectly chosen, we can obtain a laminate with inappropriate characteristics or a degraded composite.

4.3 The impact direction where the pendulum impacts has a decisive influence on the absorbed energy values. This result is caused by the high anisotropy of the material.

The impact plane influences strongly the fracture mechanism. This different mechanism can be shown by analyzing the absorbed energy values.

REFERENCES

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3. Hojo H., Okada Y. and Maeda T. "Tough-Brittle Transition of Glass Fiber Composites by Impact Testing". Advances in Chemistry Series. n°154, (1976).

TABLE 1

Average values of the Ductility Index obtained in the same conditions with different sample orientation.

Striker in parallel direction to stacking plane	Striker in perpendicular direction to stacking plane
0.54	2.26

Figure 1.- Impact energy in relation to processing pressure.

Figure 2.- Ductility index in relation to processing pressure.

Figure 3.- Sample where striker has impacted in perpendicular direction to laminate stacking.

Figure 4.- Sample where striker has impacted in parallel direction to laminate stacking.

Figure 5.- S.E.M. of the fracture where striker has impacted in parallel direction.